

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND PERCEIVED PROBLEM-SOLVING ABILITY AMONG NURSING STUDENTS HEMŞİRELİK ÖĞRENCİLERİNDE DUYGUSAL ZEKÂ İLE ALGILANAN PROBLEM ÇÖZME BECERİSİ ARASINDAKİ İLİŞKİ

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ABSTRACT

Objective: Nursing students frequently face considerable stress, uncertainty, and emotional demands during clinical training, and competencies such as emotional intelligence and effective problem-solving play a crucial role in facilitating their adaptation to clinical environments and the delivery of quality care. Therefore, this study aimed to explore the association between emotional intelligence and perceived problem-solving ability among undergraduate nursing students and to examine how these variables relate to selected sociodemographic characteristics.

Methods: This study was conducted in a descriptive and correlational design. The research was carried out with 349 undergraduate nursing students who had at least one clinical practice experience. Data were collected between May and June 2025 using an online questionnaire. The Personal Information Form, the Trait Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire–Short Form, and the Problem Solving Inventory were used for data collection. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, comparative analyses, and correlation analysis.

Results: The mean total score of the Trait Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire–Short Form was 93.44 ± 15.52 , and the mean total score of the Problem Solving Inventory was 107.21 ± 22.05 . A statistically significant negative relationship was found between emotional intelligence and perceived problem-solving ability ($p < 0.05$). Emotional intelligence and problem-solving scores were also significantly associated with age, gender, parental attitudes, and monthly income.

Conclusion: The findings indicate that an increase in emotional intelligence levels among nursing students is associated with a more adequate perception of problem-solving ability. Educational approaches that support emotional awareness, self-regulation, and interpersonal skills in nursing education may contribute to strengthening students' adaptation to clinical learning environments and their professional development.

Keywords: Clinical Learning, Emotional Intelligence, Nursing Students, Problem Solving

ÖZET

Amaç: Hemşirelik öğrencileri klinik uygulama süreçlerinde yoğun stres, belirsizlik ve duygusal yük ile karşılaşabilmekte olup, duygusal zekâ ve problem çözme becerileri klinik ortama uyum ve etkili bakım sunumu açısından önemli yeterlilikler olarak kabul edilmektedir. Bu çalışmanın amacı, lisans düzeyindeki hemşirelik öğrencilerinde duygusal zekâ ile algılanan problem çözme becerileri arasındaki ilişkinin belirlenmesi ve bu değişkenlerin sosyodemografik özellikler ile ilişkilerinin incelenmesidir. Hemşirelik öğrencileri klinik uygulama süreçlerinde yoğun stres, belirsizlik ve duygusal yük ile karşılaşabilmekte olup, duygusal zekâ ve problem çözme becerileri klinik ortama uyum ve etkili bakım sunumu açısından önemli yeterlilikler olarak kabul edilmektedir.

Gereç ve Yöntem: Bu çalışma tanımlayıcı ve ilişki arayıcı niteliktedir. Araştırma, en az bir klinik uygulama deneyimi bulunan 349 lisans öğrencisi hemşire ile yürütülmüştür. Veriler Mayıs–Haziran 2025 tarihleri arasında çevrim içi anket yöntemiyle toplanmıştır. Veri toplamada Kişisel Bilgi Formu, Duygusal Zekâ Özellik Ölçeği–Kısa Formu ve Problem Çözme Envanteri kullanılmıştır. Veriler tanımlayıcı istatistikler, karşılaştırmalı analizler ve korelasyon analizi ile değerlendirilmiştir.

Bulgular: Öğrencilerin Duygusal Zekâ Özellik Ölçeği–Kısa Formu toplam puan ortalaması 93.44 ± 15.52 ; Problem Çözme Envanteri toplam puan ortalaması 107.21 ± 22.05 'tir. Duygusal zekâ ile algılanan problem çözme becerileri arasında istatistiksel olarak anlamlı negatif yönlü bir ilişki saptanmıştır ($p < 0.05$). Duygusal zekâ ve problem çözme puanlarının yaş, cinsiyet, ebeveyn tutumları ve aylık gelir ile ilişkili olduğu belirlenmiştir.

Sonuç: Çalışma bulguları, hemşirelik öğrencilerinde duygusal zekâ düzeyinin artmasının problem çözme becerisinin daha yeterli algılanması ile ilişkili olduğunu göstermektedir. Hemşirelik eğitiminde duygusal farkındalık, öz düzenleme ve kişilerarası becerileri destekleyen eğitim yaklaşımlarının, öğrencilerin klinik öğrenme ortamlarına uyumunu ve mesleki gelişimini destekleyebileceği düşünülmektedir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Duygusal Zekâ, Hemşirelik Öğrencileri, Klinik Öğrenme, Problem Çözme

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Cite this article: Meral, K.D., Gökalp, C.S., Balalan, İ., Genç, B., Battal, I. (2026). The Relationship Between Emotional Intelligence and Perceived Problem-Solving Ability Among Nursing Students. *Gevher Nesibe Journal of Medical & Health Sciences*, 11(2), 67-77.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20538952>

INTRODUCTION

During nursing education, students encounter multiple stressors, particularly during clinical practice, including managing emergencies, witnessing life-threatening conditions, fear of making mistakes, and perceptions of inadequate professional competence. These stressors may negatively affect students' psychological well-being and learning performance, while also leading to hesitation, avoidance, and ineffective decision-making in care practices (Şenocak & Demirkıran, 2023). One of the key components of effective coping in clinical practice is the ability to define encountered situations not merely as sources of stress but as solvable problems, to generate appropriate alternatives, and to translate decisions into action. From this perspective, problem-solving ability (PSA) is regarded as a core competency closely related to clinical reasoning and decision-making, encompassing not only cognitive but also emotional and behavioral processes (Huang et al., 2023). Nursing literature emphasizes that individuals with higher PSA may demonstrate more systematic, goal-oriented, and safe care practices (Choi & Jeon, 2022). Accordingly, strengthening PSA in undergraduate nursing education, in ways that support students' capacity to cope with stressful clinical experiences, has emerged as a critical educational objective for improving clinical learning outcomes (Yeung et al., 2023).

Emotional intelligence (EI) can be described as the capability to identify and regulate one's own emotions and those of others, while incorporating emotional information into thinking processes to guide adaptive and context-sensitive behaviors (Rodríguez-Leal et al., 2024; Ruiz-Ortega et al., 2024). In nursing education, EI is considered an important competency that helps students regulate emotions, maintain emotional awareness, and respond adaptively during emotionally demanding clinical experiences (Rodríguez-Leal et al., 2024). Because nursing students face both academic and clinical stressors throughout higher education, EI is regarded as an important personal resource associated with coping with stress and adaptation to clinical learning environments (Xu et al., 2023). Recent studies have highlighted relationships between EI, perceived stress, and psychosocial resources such as self-efficacy, suggesting that these factors may be related to students' clinical adaptation, perceptions of competence, and learning experiences (Alharbi, 2025; Shubayr & Dailah, 2025). Therefore, in undergraduate nursing education, EI is considered not merely an individual trait but a socio-emotional competency that supports students' clinical learning processes and professional development (Ruiz-Ortega et al., 2024).

It has been emphasized that emotional processes may be associated with individuals' perceptions, evaluations, and responses to problems; therefore, problem solving is regarded as a multidimensional construct involving both cognitive and emotional components. Nursing students commonly experience uncertain and time-pressured clinical environments involving substantial emotional challenges, underscoring the importance of emotional awareness and self-regulation in problem-solving processes (Ndawo, 2021). Accordingly, EI is considered an important resource related to how nursing students respond to clinical problems and decision-making processes. Studies conducted with nursing students have reported significant relationships between EI and PSA (Deng et al., 2023; Mohamed Ragab et al., 2022; Selçuk Tosun et al., 2025).

Earlier studies have reported that EI is associated with key outcomes in nursing students, such as clinical competence and the ability to make effective clinical decisions. (Alharbi, 2025; Jawabreh, 2024). Nevertheless, within undergraduate nursing education, EI and PSA have generally been investigated independently in relation to various clinical outcomes, and there remains limited evidence regarding their combined role in students' perceptions of managing clinical challenges. Additionally, studies examining determinants of problem-solving skills suggest that emotional and cognitive processes may be interrelated in shaping students' coping and adjustment during clinical practice (Selçuk Tosun et al., 2025). These considerations underscore the need for a more integrated perspective to better understand how nursing students interpret and evaluate the difficulties they encounter in clinical learning settings.

Accordingly, the present study examined EI and perceived PSA together in the context of coping with challenges experienced during clinical training. Specifically, the study aimed to determine the relationship between EI levels and perceived PSA among undergraduate nursing students.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Design

This study was conducted using a descriptive cross-sectional design to examine the relationship between EI levels and perceived PSA among undergraduate nursing students. The study was reported in line with the Strengthening the Reporting of Observational Studies in Epidemiology (STROBE) guidelines for observational studies.

Study population and sample

The study was carried out between May and June 2025 with undergraduate nursing students enrolled in the Department of Nursing at the Faculty of Health Sciences of a foundation university located in western XX. The study population consisted of 533 nursing students who had completed at least one semester of clinical practice in a hospital setting.

The sample size was calculated using G*Power version 3.1 software (Faul et al., 2007). The minimum required sample size was determined by considering a previous study examining the relationship between emotional intelligence and problem-solving skills (İbici Akça & Gökbulut, 2025). Considering an effect size corresponding to a weak correlation ($r = 0.16$), a 95% confidence level ($\alpha = 0.05$), and 80% statistical power ($1-\beta$), the minimum required sample size was calculated as 304. A total of 349 students who provided voluntary consent and fully completed the data collection tools were included in the study. A convenience sampling approach was employed to recruit participants.

Instruments

Data were collected using a Sociodemographic Information Form, the Trait Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire–Short Form (TEIQue-SF), and the Problem Solving Inventory (PSI).

Sociodemographic Information Form

A Sociodemographic Information Form was prepared by the researchers based on prior literature and contained questions addressing participants' age, gender, year of study, family background, parental education and occupational status, perceived economic level, living arrangements, and clinical practice experience (Deng et al., 2023; Shahbazi et al., 2018).

TEIQue-SF

The measure was adapted from the TEIQue developed by Petrides and Furnham (Petrides, 2009), and its Turkish psychometric properties were confirmed by Deniz, Özer, and Işık (Deniz et al., 2013). It contains 20 items distributed across four dimensions—well-being, self-control, emotionality, and sociability. Items are evaluated on a 7-point Likert scale ranging from strong disagreement to strong agreement, and reverse-coded items are scored accordingly. Higher total scores represent higher TEIQue levels. In this study, the scale demonstrated acceptable reliability (Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.791$).

PSI

This scale was developed by Heppner and Petersen (Heppner & Petersen, 1982) to assess individuals' approaches to problem solving in everyday life. The Turkish validity and reliability study was conducted by Şahin et al. (Şahin et al., 1993). It consists of 35 items and includes six subscales: impulsive approach, reflective approach, avoidant approach, evaluative approach, self-confident approach, and planned approach. Items are rated on a 6-point Likert scale, and some items are reverse-coded. Higher total scores indicate a perception of inadequate problem-solving ability, whereas lower scores indicate a perception of adequate PSA. In the present study, the internal consistency of the scale was high, with a Cronbach's α coefficient of $\alpha = 0.881$.

Data collection

Data were collected between May and June 2025 after obtaining the necessary permissions from the faculty administration and providing participants with information about the purpose and scope of the study. Participation was voluntary, and informed consent was obtained from all participants. Students were approached face-to-face during the academic term and informed about the study. Individuals who agreed to participate received a link directing them to an online questionnaire used to collect study data. The introductory section of the survey explained the study objectives, confidentiality principles, and the

voluntary basis of participation. Participants provided digital informed consent before proceeding. The survey platform was set to accept only one response per participant and did not allow submission of partially completed forms. To enhance methodological rigor and reduce bias, validated instruments were used, and system settings were applied to prevent duplicate or incomplete responses.

Statistical analysis

All statistical procedures were performed with IBM SPSS Statistics (version 26.0). Normality assumptions were evaluated using the Kolmogorov–Smirnov test prior to selecting parametric or non-parametric analyses. Descriptive measures such as mean values, standard deviations, frequencies, and percentages were used to describe the dataset. Depending on distribution characteristics, parametric tests (Student’s t-test and one-way ANOVA) or non-parametric tests (Mann–Whitney U and Kruskal–Wallis) were applied for group comparisons. Associations between variables were evaluated using Pearson correlation for normally distributed data and Spearman correlation for non-normally distributed variables. All statistical analyses were conducted at the 95% confidence level, and p-values < 0.05 were considered statistically significant.

Ethical approval

Ethical approval for the study was obtained from the Ethics Committee of İstanbul Gelişim University (approval date: 09 May 2025; meeting number: 2025/07; decision number: 2025-07/33). The study was conducted in accordance with the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, and participation was based on voluntary involvement.

RESULTS

The sociodemographic and education-related characteristics of the participating nursing students are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Sociodemographic and Education-Related Characteristics of Nursing Students (n = 349)

Variables	n	%
Age (years)		
17-18	16	4.60
19-20	66	18.90
21-22	105	30.10
≥23	162	46.40
Gender		
Female	256	73.40
Male	93	26.60
Family structure		
Extended family	106	30.30
Nuclear family	227	65.10
Single-parent family (living with mother or father only)	10	2.90
Step-parent family (mother or father remarried)	6	1.70
Year of study		
First year	52	14.90
Second year	58	16.60
Third year	106	30.40
Fourth year	133	38.10
Perceived parental attitude		
Indifferent	11	3.20
Overprotective	146	41.80
Inconsistent	6	1.70
Democratic	28	8.00
Supportive	158	45.30
Perceived monthly income		
Very low	34	9.70
Low	77	22.10

Moderate	193	55.30
High	45	12.90
Choosing the nursing program willingly		
Yes	245	70.20
No	46	13.20
Undecided	58	16.60

Descriptive statistical methods (mean, standard deviation, frequency, and percentage) were used.

The subscale and total scores of the TEIQue and the PSI are presented in Table 2. The mean total score of the TEIQue was 93.44 ± 15.52 , while the mean total score of the PSI was 107.21 ± 22.05 (see Table 2).

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics of TEIQue-SF and PSI Among Nursing Students (n = 349).

Scale / Subscale	Mean \pm SD
TEIQue	
Well-being	19.54 \pm 4.87
Self-control	17.05 \pm 4.61
Emotionality	18.28 \pm 3.81
Sociability	19.33 \pm 4.25
Total emotional intelligence score	93.44 \pm 15.52
PSI	
Impulsive approach	30.79 \pm 6.78
Reflective approach	16.89 \pm 5.94
Avoidant approach	12.36 \pm 4.98
Evaluative approach	10.07 \pm 4.03
Self-confident approach	23.63 \pm 6.46
Planned approach	13.47 \pm 5.03
Total problem-solving score	107.21 \pm 22.05

Values are presented as mean \pm standard deviation.

The relationships between participants' sociodemographic characteristics and the total scores of the TEIQue and the PSI are presented in Table 3. According to the analysis results, statistically significant associations were found between age and the total EI score of nursing students, gender and the total problem-solving score, perceived parental attitude and the total problem-solving score, and monthly income and the total EI score ($p < 0.05$) (see Table 3).

Table 3. Relationships between participants' personal characteristics and total scores of the TEIQue-SF and the PSI (n = 349).

Variable	TEIQue (Mean \pm SD)	<i>p</i>	PSI (Mean \pm SD)	<i>p</i>
Age (years)				
17-18	86.25 \pm 15.360	0.049	107.13 \pm 19.926	0.933
19-20	92.14 \pm 1.390		108.82 \pm 18.291	
21-22	92.05 \pm 14.916		106.71 \pm 22.857	
≥ 23	95.59 \pm 16.783		106.90 \pm 23.254	
Gender				
Female	93.99 \pm 15.17	0.275	104.88 \pm 22.25	0.001
Male	91.94 \pm 16.46		113.63 \pm 20.26	
Year of study				
First year	89.62 \pm 13.52	0.227	109.15 \pm 17.24	0.407
Second year	92.76 \pm 15.31		105.55 \pm 21.90	
Third year	94.76 \pm 15.52		109.56 \pm 23.28	
Fourth year	94.18 \pm 16.24		105.32 \pm 22.76	

Perceived parental attitude				
Indifferent	86.55 ± 15.14		114.91 ± 20.07	
Overprotective	91.31 ± 15.16		103.52 ± 20.64	
Inconsistent	90.83 ± 20.81	0.067	110.33 ± 5.82	0.010
Democratic	95.25 ± 19.58		118.61 ± 20.95	
Supportive	95.67 ± 14.63		107.96 ± 23.27	
Perceived monthly income				
Very low	86.26 ± 14.99		106.21 ± 22.28	
Low	89.47 ± 14.14	0.001	107.42 ± 20.41	0.246
Moderate	95.69 ± 15.25		105.90 ± 22.13	
High	96.02 ± 16.74		113.27 ± 23.89	
Choosing the nursing program willingly				
Yes	94.51 ± 14.97		106.15 ± 22.29	
No	89.54 ± 17.42	0.103	111.00 ± 24.85	0.334
Undecided	92.02 ± 15.90		108.72 ± 18.31	

Student's t-test, Mann-Whitney U test, one-way ANOVA, and Kruskal-Wallis test were used. $p < .05$ was considered significant.

The analysis revealed a statistically significant negative correlation between the total TEIQue-SF score and the total PSI score ($r = -0.184$, $p = 0.001$). Among the TEIQue-SF subscales, self-control and emotionality demonstrated the most consistent significant correlations with PSI scores. Specifically, self-control was negatively correlated with the total PSI score ($r = -0.173$, $p = 0.001$), and emotionality was negatively correlated with the total PSI score ($r = -0.157$, $p = 0.003$). Although the overall correlation was weak, some subscale-level associations appeared relatively more pronounced, particularly between well-being and avoidant approach ($r = -0.239$, $p = 0.001$) and between emotionality and planned approach ($r = -0.204$, $p = 0.001$). Significant positive correlations were also observed among the PSI subscales and among the TEIQue-SF subscales (see Table 4).

Table 4. Correlations Between TEIQue-SF Subscales and PSI Subscales Among Nursing Students (n = 349)

	Impulsive approach	Reflective approach	Avoidant approach	Evaluative approach	Self-confident approach	Planned approach	Total problem-solving score	Well-being	Self-control	Emotionality	Sociability	Total emotional intelligence score
Impulsive approach		,159	465	,155	,038	,240	275	,112	,035	099	085	000
Reflective approach			003	001	478	001	001	037	514	064	113	993
Avoidant approach	,159			720	755	823	792	063	,078	,190	,080	,103
Evaluative approach			011	001	001	001	001	237	145	001	137	055
Self-confident approach	465	136		163	317	177	568	,239	,195	,016	,015	,167
Planned approach				001	001	001	001	001	001	770	776	002
Total problem-solving score	,155	720	163**		731	782	759	,004	,136	,183	,127	,150
Well-being					001	001	001		939	011	001	018
Self-control	,038	755	317	731		782	869	,040	,116	,181	,135	,155
Emotionality	478	001	001	001	001	001	001	459	030	001	012	004

Planned approach	,240	823	177	782	782		788	,009	,169	,204	,178	,202
	001	001	001	001	001	001	001	861	002	001	001	001
Total problem-solving score	275	792	568	759	869	788		,086	,173	,157	,102	,184
	001	001	001	001	001	001		110	001	003	057	001
Well-being	,112	063	,239	,004	,040	,009	,086		235	131	419	673
	037	237	001	939	459	861	110		001	014	001	001
Self-control	,035	,078	,195	,136	,116	,169	,173	235		354	295	660
	514	145	001	011	030	002	001	001	001	001	001	001
Emotionality	099	,190	,016	,183	,181	,204	,157	131	354		382	630
	064	001	770	001	001	001	003	014	001	001	001	001
Sociability	085	,080	,015	,127	,135	,178	,102	419	295	382		735
	113	137	776	018	012	001	057	001	001	001	001	001
Total emotional intelligence score	000	,103	,167	,150	,155	,202	,184	673	660	630	735	
	993	055	002	005	004	001	001	001	001	001	001	

r = correlation coefficient. Pearson and Spearman correlation analyses were used. $p < .05$ was considered significant

DISCUSSION

The findings of this study revealed a statistically significant but weak negative association between nursing students' trait EI and their perceived PSA. Given that higher PSI scores reflect a perception of inadequate PSA, this finding suggests that students with higher emotional intelligence may perceive themselves as more competent in their problem-solving processes. Previous studies have reported positive relationships between EI and PSA (Mohamed Ragab et al., 2022; Selçuk Tosun et al., 2025). When the reverse-scoring structure of the measurement instrument is taken into account, the direction of the relationship identified in the present study appears to be consistent with the existing literature. EI may be associated with individuals' perceptions of problems as more manageable through components such as self-awareness, emotion regulation, and coping with stress, which in turn may be related to self-evaluation of the problem-solving process (Ndawo, 2021; Shahbazi et al., 2018). Within the context of the present sample, this finding indicates that PSA may be considered not only as a cognitive competency but also as a subjective evaluative process reflecting students' perceptions of their own problem-solving capacities. Subscale-level analyses further demonstrated that self-control and emotionality were among the emotional intelligence dimensions most consistently associated with perceived problem-solving scores. Students with higher self-control may regulate emotional reactions more effectively in stressful clinical situations, which may influence how they evaluate their ability to cope with problems. Similarly, emotional awareness and emotion regulation skills may be associated with students' evaluation of challenging clinical situations. Emotional regulation, emotional readiness, and reflective approaches have been emphasized as factors that may support effective problem-solving and decision-making processes (Ndawo, 2021). In addition, some subscale-level associations appeared more pronounced than the overall correlation, particularly those involving well-being, emotionality, and avoidant or planned problem-solving approaches. These findings suggest that different emotional competencies may be associated with nursing students' perceptions of their problem-solving abilities in different ways.

The average total TEIQue score was 93.44 ± 15.52 , whereas the PSI total score averaged 107.21 ± 22.05 . These results suggest that nursing students' EI levels were generally in the moderate-to-high range. In contrast, they may be more cautious in self-evaluating their problem-solving processes. Although previous studies have reported that nursing students' EI levels are generally moderate or above, PSA has been reported to be associated with students' perceptions of self-confidence and self-evaluation in clinical practice settings (Deng et al., 2023; Selçuk Tosun et al., 2025). This finding suggests that having well-developed emotional competencies is not necessarily associated with perceiving one's PSA as sufficient and that self-evaluation processes should be considered as a distinct component within the context of clinical learning. Similarly, it has been reported that PSA in clinical environments depends not only on technical knowledge but also on students' self-evaluation and perceived self-confidence (Huang et al., 2023).

The findings further suggest that students' evaluations of their problem-solving processes may be associated not only with cognitive competencies but also with individual characteristics. The results indicated a statistically significant relationship between participants' age and their EI levels. Previous research has reported that EI among nursing students may increase with age and progression through the educational process (Budler et al., 2022; Razghandi et al., 2025). This relationship may be associated with students' increasing clinical and academic experience, which may enable more effective use of emotional awareness and emotion regulation skills. Clinical practice experience has been reported to be associated with students' ability to recognize and regulate emotional responses and is viewed as a key element of professional development (Rodríguez-Leal et al., 2024). From this perspective, age is not directly associated with problem-solving ability but may indirectly contribute to the development of students' emotional skills.

Similarly, the relationships observed between gender, perceived problem-solving ability, monthly income, and parental attitudes indicate that students' psychosocial resources and environmental conditions may be associated with the development of both cognitive and emotional competencies during clinical learning. The gender differences observed in perceived PSA may be linked to variations in students' approaches to clinical decision-making. Prior studies also indicate that nursing students' clinical decision-making skills, self-confidence, and problem-solving abilities may differ by gender (Arkan et al., 2023; Candan Dönmez et al., 2025). Moreover, the associations between monthly income, parental attitudes, and emotional and problem-solving processes indicate that students' psychosocial resources may be related to their cognitive and emotional competencies within the clinical learning context (Shubayr & Dailah, 2025; Xu et al., 2023).

Study Limitations

Some limitations of this research should be acknowledged. The study was conducted among nursing students from a single foundation university, which may restrict the broader applicability of the results. However, the inclusion of students from different academic years and with diverse sociodemographic characteristics may have partially mitigated this limitation. Second, due to the cross-sectional design, causal relationships between EI and perceived PSA could not be established. Additionally, the weak magnitude of the observed correlation should be considered when interpreting the findings. Finally, the use of self-report measurement instruments may have introduced bias related to participants' perceptions and self-evaluations. Future research using longitudinal designs, multicenter samples, and mixed-method approaches could offer deeper insight into these relationships.

CONCLUSION

This study revealed a statistically significant but weak association EI levels and perceived PSA in undergraduate nursing students. Although participants generally demonstrated moderate to high EI levels, they did not always perceive themselves as sufficiently competent in managing problem-solving processes. This relationship suggests that students' emotional awareness and regulation skills may be related to how they approach and cope with clinical challenges encountered during practice. These results emphasize the importance of addressing emotional and cognitive competencies together within nursing education.

From an educational perspective, the identified association implies that problem-solving in nursing education extends beyond technical and cognitive aspects. Integrating students' emotional and

psychosocial characteristics into clinical learning environments may be associated with enhanced confidence and self-perception in managing clinical problems. While this study did not evaluate specific educational interventions, the results highlight the potential value of educational approaches that promote reflective learning, emotional awareness, and self-insight during preparation for clinical practice. Future research may further investigate the effectiveness of such strategies in strengthening students' emotional and cognitive readiness for clinical settings.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declared no potential conflicts of interest concerning the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Author Contributions

The authors declare that they have contributed equally to the article. All authors declare that they have seen/read and approved the final version of the article ready for publication.

Funding

This study received no financial support from any funding agency.

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